

A MECHANISM BASED DAMAGE MESO-MODEL FOR FIBER REINFORCED LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: A ply-scale model for simulation of progressive damage in fiber reinforced laminates under plane stress is presented. The proposed continuum damage model is based on meso-scopic damage mechanisms and models regarding their effect on material stiffness. Focusing on matrix dominated failure modes, the damage behavior is split into two contributions; damage evolution and damage effect. The prior prescribes the increase of damage with load by a scalar-valued evolution law. The latter predicts the effect of the damage state on material stiffness depending on the current stress state and failure mode using a fourth order tensor equation. This way the relevant damage characteristics are captured and the full 3D elasticity tensor of the damaged material is obtained requiring only few model parameters. Combining the damage model with classical lamination theory, the behavior of laminates under plane stress states is predicted. Model predictions agree well with experimental test data from the literature.

KEYWORDS: progressive damage, fiber reinforced laminates, continuum damage mechanics, lamination theory, Puck failure criterion, matrix failure mechanisms

INTRODUCTION

With laminates made of fiber reinforced polymers (FRP) becoming more and more important for structural application, there is an increasing need for accurate and reliable prediction of the behavior of such laminates and components made thereof. An important aspect of FRP material behavior is the reduction of stiffness due to damage, attributed mainly to matrix cracking [1, 2]. This effect can be modeled in a computationally efficient way by continuum damage modeling [3, 4], where the actual (discontinuous) material is replaced by a homogenized material, showing the same effective material behavior. This way a constitutive law relating stresses, strains, and damage can be formulated on the ply-level. For FRP laminates, several damage models have been presented in the literature (e.g. [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11]). These models have been shown to agree well with experimental data for damage under a combination of transverse tension and in-plane shear stresses. Most of the models are also able to account for stiffness recovery, an effect due to the closing of pre-existing cracks, but assume no decrease of stiffness in the case of uniaxial transverse compression. This is in contrast to experimental results, which show stiffness reduction in transverse compression tests of UD specimens (e.g. [12]).

In the present work, a ply-level constitutive model accounting for damage in fiber reinforced laminates is presented. The objective is to develop a model for damage due to matrix dominated failure modes under quasi-static loading, that needs only few, easily identifiable damage parameters, but at the same time is able to capture the relevant characteristics of damage. The fundamental assumption of the continuum damage model is that under increasing load damage develops in the form of cracks, whose orientations depend on the failure mode. Once damage has evolved in the material it cannot decrease anymore, i.e. the damage does not ‘heal’. But the effect of damage on material stiffness can vary depending on the current stress state. For example, if cracks are closed, they have less effect on stiffness since forces can be transmitted over the contacting crack faces (‘stiffness recovery’).

To account for these two separate aspects of damage, the model is strictly divided into two independent parts, damage evolution and damage effect. In the first part of the model, the increase of damage as function of some maximum load measure is described by a damage evolution law, i.e. the amount of damage in the material depends on the load history. To this end a stress based load measure and corresponding damage modes are derived based on Puck’s failure hypotheses for FRP laminates [9, 13]. In a second step, the effect of damage on stiffness as function of the current stress state is predicted by recourse to a mean field method. This method is not intended to model the effect of actual cracks quantitatively, but provides a set of equations to derive a thermodynamically consistent elasticity tensor for the damaged material that can qualitatively capture the damage effect. By this approach not only stiffness degradation but also the effects of stiffness recovery and oblique cracking can be taken into account. In the formulation of the damage model plane stress is assumed, hence, global delamination is not captured, also secondary failure mechanisms (e.g. diffuse delamination) are not considered. However, the full 3D elasticity tensor of the damaged material is predicted. Damage due to fiber failure is not included in the model. Fiber failure in one ply typically leads to substantial damage in adjacent layers too, and is considered as ultimate laminate failure. The ply damage model is combined with classical lamination theory to predict the damage behavior of laminates, but can also be implemented as a constitutive law in a finite element code for structural analysis. It can be used for arbitrary loading paths, provided that there is no change of crack orientation during the load history.

EVOLUTION OF DAMAGE

The first task in developing the damage model is the definition of damage state variable(s), a load measure, and their relation. As long as there is no change of crack orientation during loading a single scalar variable is sufficient to describe the damage state. In the present work, the damage state is quantified by the variable ξ , which is a fictitious quantity and not related to the actual crack density in the material. In order to define a damage evolution law, the damage state is linked to a factor of effort, f_E . It is derived based on the hypothesis that the laws for stress interaction in multiaxial stress states are the same for first ply failure (FPF) and damage prediction. Therefore, the severity of a given stress state can be measured by comparing it to a FPF surface. Using the Puck FPF criterion for plane stress states (‘Puck 2D’) the factor of effort is computed from

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = f_E \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{\text{FPF}} \quad , \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the current ply stress state, and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{\text{FPF}}$ is the corresponding FPF-stress state given by Puck 2D (cf. Fig. 1, left). A detailed discription of the Puck 2D criterion in the

Figure 1: Definition of factor of effort, f_E , (left), and damage evolution law, $\xi(f_E)$, depending on evolution parameter, κ , (right).

present notation is given in [13]. By this definition $f_E = 1$ when the stress state reaches the FPF surface. Consequently, any damage evolving at $f_E < 1$ can be considered as micro-damage, while $f_E > 1$ corresponds to meso-damage.

The evolution law needs to follow some general characteristics of damage evolution in FRP laminates reported e.g. in [1, 9]. As long as the load is below a certain threshold, given by f_E^{thr} in our model, no damage occurs. Above this threshold, damage starts to develop and progresses until saturation is reached. At saturation, no more matrix cracks are created by a further increase of load. An evolution law fulfilling these requirements is given by

$$\frac{\xi}{\xi_{\text{sat}}} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } f_E \leq f_E^{\text{thr}} = \frac{1}{1+\kappa} \\ 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{(f_E(1+\kappa)-1)^2}{2\kappa^2}\right) & \text{for } f_E \geq f_E^{\text{thr}} = \frac{1}{1+\kappa} \end{cases}, \quad (2)$$

with evolution parameter, κ , and the damage state variable at saturation, ξ_{sat} . The evolution parameter κ is related to how quickly damage advances with an increase of the factor of effort, where the evolution law converges to the step function for $\kappa \rightarrow 0$ (cf. Fig. 1, right). The damage state at FPF is given by $\xi^{\text{FPF}}/\xi_{\text{sat}} = \text{const.}$ and the onset of damage depends solely on the parameter κ (cf. Eqn. 2) which is a function of the stress state. In agreement with the previous assumption that the laws for FPF stress interactions also apply to damage, a damage onset surface is defined. This is done by scaling the FPF surface using the evolution parameters for in-plane shear, κ_{12} , transverse tension, κ_{22}^t , and transverse compression, κ_{22}^c , determined from experimental testing. For a given stress state the corresponding stress states at FPF, σ^{FPF} , and damage onset, σ^{thr} , can then be determined as illustrated in Fig. 2. Finally, the value of κ for any stress state is given by

$$\kappa = \frac{1}{f_E^{\text{thr}}} - 1 \quad \text{with} \quad f_E^{\text{thr}} \sigma^{\text{FPF}} = \sigma^{\text{thr}}. \quad (3)$$

When saturation is reached in one ply of a laminate, there is no further increase of matrix cracking, instead other damage mechanisms come into effect (e.g. diffuse delamination) which are not covered by the model. Therefore this damage state is considered as final matrix failure. It should be noted that diffuse delamination may also start prior to saturation and that damage predictions at damage states close to saturation should be treated with caution. It has been reported, though, that in thin plies saturation is typically reached before significant delaminations appear [1, 5].

Figure 2: Damage and failure surfaces of a typical carbon fiber/epoxy material in σ_{22} - σ_{12} stress space and their application to define $\kappa(\boldsymbol{\sigma})$.

EFFECT OF DAMAGE

The effect of damage on the material behavior is based on the assumption that it can be approximated by oblate spheroidal inclusions within the initial ply material (cf. Fig. 3, left). It is independent of how the damage was created and applies to both the micro- and meso-damage regime. The initial ply material is taken to be homogeneous and transversally isotropic with respect to the ply coordinate system 1-2-3. The inclusions are aligned, oblate spheroids with axes referred to the fracture plane coordinate system l-n-t. The aspect ratio normal to the fracture plane, e_n , is much smaller than one. Note that the inclusions are not intended to model the actual cracks in the material, rather they are used to derive a thermodynamically consistent elasticity tensor using the Mori-Tanaka Method (MTM) [14, 15], a mean field method known from mechanics of materials. This way the damage effect is captured qualitatively. Based on the formulation of Tandon and Weng [16], the compliance tensor of the damaged material is given by the 4th order tensor equation

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{C}^d &= \left\{ \mathbf{I} - \xi [(\mathbf{E}^{\text{incl}} - \mathbf{E}^0) : (\mathbf{S} - \xi(\mathbf{S} - \mathbf{I})) + \mathbf{E}^0]^{-1} : [\mathbf{E}^{\text{incl}} - \mathbf{E}^0] \right\} : \mathbf{C}^0 \\ &= \left\{ \mathbf{I} + \xi [(\mathbf{E}^0 - \mathbf{E}^{\text{incl}})^{-1} : \mathbf{E}^{\text{incl}} + (1 - \xi)(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{S})]^{-1} \right\} : \mathbf{C}^0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Here, \mathbf{E}^{incl} denotes the elasticity tensor of the fictitious inclusions, \mathbf{E}^0 and \mathbf{C}^0 are the elasticity and compliance tensors of the initial (undamaged) material, respectively, \mathbf{S} is the Eshelby tensor, and \mathbf{I} is the 4th order identity tensor. The Eshelby tensor is constant and depends on initial material properties and inclusion geometry. In order to compute the compliance tensor of the damaged material from Eqn. 4, the inclusion stiffness and orientation are defined depending on the damage mode.

If normal stresses on the fracture plane are tensile, cracks are ‘open’, i.e. there is no contact between crack faces, consequently no forces can be transmitted across the cracks. In this case the inclusion elasticity tensor is set to zero and Eqn. 4 simplifies to a material containing voids

$$\mathbf{C}^{\text{d,open}} \equiv \mathbf{C}^d|_{\mathbf{E}^{\text{incl}}=0} = \left[\mathbf{I} + \frac{\xi}{1 - \xi} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{S})^{-1} \right] : \mathbf{C}^0 \quad (5)$$

In the case of compressive normal stresses on the crack plane the cracks are closed, meaning that crack faces are in contact and no longer free of tractions. As a result, forces can be

Figure 3: Orientation of Mori-Tanaka inclusions with respect to ply- and fracture plane coordinate systems (left); failure modes according to Puck 2D [9, 13](right).

transmitted across the cracks which leads to the recovery of material stiffness. In the model, this effect is attained by defining a non-zero inclusion elasticity tensor as

$$\mathbf{E}^{\text{incl}} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} E_{\parallel}^0 & E_{\text{ln}}^0 & E_{\text{lt}}^0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ E_{\text{ln}}^0 & E_{\text{nn}}^0 & E_{\text{nt}}^0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ E_{\text{lt}}^0 & E_{\text{nt}}^0 & E_{\text{tt}}^0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \mu_{\text{D}}|\sigma_{\text{nn}}| & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{\text{lt}}^0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \mu_{\text{D}}|\sigma_{\text{nn}}| \end{pmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

$$(\boldsymbol{\sigma} = [\sigma_{\parallel}, \sigma_{\text{nn}}, \sigma_{\text{tt}}, \sigma_{\text{ln}}, \sigma_{\text{lt}}, \sigma_{\text{nt}}]^{\text{T}}, \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = [\varepsilon_{\parallel}, \varepsilon_{\text{nn}}, \varepsilon_{\text{tt}}, 2\varepsilon_{\text{ln}}, 2\varepsilon_{\text{lt}}, 2\varepsilon_{\text{nt}}]^{\text{T}})$$

with stiffnesses set to the initial material's values, $()^0$, except for the shear moduli $G_{\text{ln}}^{\text{incl}}$ and $G_{\text{nt}}^{\text{incl}}$. These are a function of the pressure on the crack face as $G_{\text{ln}}^{\text{incl}} = G_{\text{nt}}^{\text{incl}} = \mu_{\text{D}}|\sigma_{\text{nn}}|$. The factor μ_{D} is a material parameter introduced to account for shear stiffness recovery. Note that due to the initial material being transversally isotropic, the initial values in Eqn. 6 are the same as those referenced to the ply coordinate system ($E_{\parallel}^0 = E_{11}^0, E_{\text{nn}}^0 = E_{\text{tt}}^0 = E_{22}^0, E_{\text{ln}}^0 = E_{\text{lt}}^0 = E_{12}^0, E_{\text{nt}}^0 = E_{\text{tt}}^0 = E_{23}^0, G_{\text{lt}}^0 = G_{13}^0$).

If the ply and fracture plane coordinate systems are not aligned (i.e. $\theta_{fp} \neq 0$), the compliance tensor given by Eqn. 4 needs to be transformed to ply coordinates through rotation by the angle θ_{fp} . The resulting compliance tensor

$$\mathbf{C}^{\text{d}}(\theta_{fp}) = \begin{pmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & C_{26} \\ C_{13} & C_{23} & C_{33} & 0 & 0 & C_{36} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} & C_{45} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{45} & C_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & C_{26} & C_{36} & 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

resembles that of a monoclinic material, with shear/extension coupling in the 2/3 coordinate plane. The damage mode caused by a given stress state is determined by the Puck failure criterion [9, 13] (cf. Fig. 3, right). In the case of tensile normal stresses in direction transverse to the fibers, failure mode A is predicted, which corresponds to open cracks and

a fracture plane orientation of $\theta_{\text{fp}} = 0$. Consequently, the compliance tensor for a material damaged under a mode A load case is given by Eqn. 5. Since the fracture plane is aligned with the ply coordinate system, no rotation of the material tensor is necessary.

Under transverse compression, cracks are closed and the inclusion elasticity tensor given by Eqn. 6 is used to compute the damaged material compliance from Eqn. 4. The fracture plane orientation depends on the ratio between shear and compressive stresses. If shear stresses are dominant, mode B failure will occur, where the fracture plane is still aligned with the ply coordinate system. If compressive stresses are high compared to in-plane shear stresses, they lead to mode C failure with a slanted fracture plane and a maximum inclination at uniaxial compression of $\theta_{\text{fp}} \sim 52^\circ$ (for definition of θ_{fp} see [9, 13]). For mode C, the material transformation to ply coordinates needs to be performed.

EXAMPLE – PARAMETER IDENTIFICATION

In order to fully calibrate the damage model, six parameters need to be identified based on experimental data from three tests. The evolution parameters for in-plane shear, transverse compression, and transverse tension, κ_{12} , κ_{22}^c , and κ_{22}^t , respectively, can be derived from the stress-strain data of the corresponding load cases. The procedure is illustrated in Fig. 4 for the carbon fiber/epoxy material AS4/3501-6 [11, 12, 17]. Note, that for transverse tension the degradation of laminate Young’s modulus, E_x , vs. laminate stress, σ_{xx} , of a 0/90-laminate under uniaxial tension is plotted, while the ply stress-strain curves are displayed for the other two load cases. Damage onset is assumed to correspond to the first deviation from linear material behavior. Thus, the ply stress at damage onset for each of the three load cases can be identified from the experimental curves in Fig. 4. Knowing the corresponding FPF stresses of the material, which are given in [12], the three evolution parameters can be computed from Eqn. 3 as $\kappa_{12} = 1.63$, $\kappa_{22}^c = 0.54$, and $\kappa_{22}^t = 0.1$.

The damage effect depends on the three parameters inclusion aspect ratio, e_n , damage state variable at saturation, ξ_{sat} , and shear stiffness recovery factor, μ_D . They are considered to be constants, i.e. they do not depend on load or failure mode. Due to the definition of inclusion stiffness given in the previous section there is no influence of μ_D on damage for mode A stress states. Therefore, only e_n and ξ_{sat} are subject to parameter identification by recourse to the experimental curves of simple shear and transverse tension. For the given material they are determined as $e_n = 0.035$ and $\xi_{\text{sat}} = 0.2$. Based on the compressive material behavior the parameter for shear stiffness recovery is determined as $\mu_D = 15$. The material data for AS4/3501-6 including damage parameters are summed up in Table 1. Experimental data are taken from [12, 17]. As can be seen from Fig. 4, the model predictions compare well with experimental results for all three load cases.

EXAMPLE – COMPARISON SINGLE-PLY VS. LAMINATE TEST

In experimental testing some stress states are difficult to produce in UD-laminates. This problem is often solved by testing multi-directional laminates and deriving ply stress-strain relations based on lamination theory. In Fig. 5 the shear stress-shear strain behavior of an E-glass/epoxy material determined from two different tests methods [19] is compared (for material data see Table 2). The solid line (‘exp. UD-layer’) corresponds to the data obtained experimentally by torsion of a tube with fiber orientation in hoop direction. The dashed lines are derived from biaxial testing of $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates under stress ratio

Table 1: Material data and damage parameters of carbon fiber/epoxy UD-layer, AS₄/3501-6 [12].

elastic constants					
E_1	$E_2 = E_3$	$G_{12} = G_{13}$	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	ν_{23}	
[GPa]	[GPa]	[GPa]			
126	11	6.6	0.28	0.4	
strength data					
	R_{11}	R_{22}	R_{12}	p_{12}	p_{23}
	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]		
tension	1950	48	79	0.35 *	0.27 *
compression	1480	200	79	0.3 *	0.27 *
damage evolution			damage effect		
κ_{12}	κ_{22}^t	κ_{22}^c	e_n	ξ_{sat}	μ_D
1.63	0.1	0.54	0.035	0.2	15

* following Puck's guidelines for carbon fiber materials [18]

Figure 4: Comparison of model and experimental results concerning the damage behavior of AS₄/3501-6 carbon/epoxy subjected to in-plane simple shear stress (a); uni-axial transverse compressive stress [12] (b); uni-axial transverse tensile stress [17] (c).

$\sigma_{xx}/\sigma_{yy} = -1$, which leads to simple in-plane shear in each individual layer. According to lamination theory, there should be no difference between the two load cases, since both produce the same ply stress state. From Fig. 5 it can be seen, however, that data derived from the single ply and laminate tests differ.

Assuming that the curve ‘exp. UD-layer’ represents the actual shear behavior of a single ply, it is used to determine the relevant damage model parameters as $\kappa_{12} = 0.6$, $e_2 =$

Figure 5: Damage behavior of single ply vs. ply in laminate; experimental results [19] and model predictions.

0.086, $\xi_{\text{sat}} = 0.7$ (Fig. 5, ‘model, no curing stresses’). By combining the damage model with lamination theory the damage behavior of the $\pm 45^\circ$ laminate is predicted. As expected, there is no difference between the single ply and laminate tests according to the model. It is known, however, that the curing process of polymers leads to shrinkage due to thermal and chemical effects. In FRPs the shrinkage is different in fiber and transverse directions (e.g. for the given material 0.14% in transverse, and 0% in longitudinal direction [19]), which leads to residual curing stresses in multi-directional laminates. If the stresses due to obstruction of shrinkage are included in the model of the $\pm 45^\circ$ laminate test (Fig. 5, ‘model, incl. curing stresses’), the agreement between the model prediction and $\pm 45^\circ$ tests is excellent. Note, that κ_{22}^t is required for this stress state. Although it is assumed as $\kappa_{22}^t = 0.1$, the choice has little influence on the results which show that curing stresses can be responsible for the apparent difference in material behavior obtained by different test methods. Again, it has to be noted that the model is only realistic as long as no secondary failure mechanisms occur.

CONCLUSIONS

In the present work, a damage meso-model for FRP laminates is proposed, which is based on physical failure mechanisms postulated by the Puck failure criterion for plane stress states. The model is strictly divided into two contributions, damage evolution and damage effect. In the present work a scalar equation is used to define an evolution law for damage under quasi static loading. To capture the effect of damage on ply stiffness a fourth order tensor equation provided by the Mori-Tanaka method is used to derive a thermodynamically consistent elasticity tensor for the damaged material. By distinction of various matrix failure modes, the effects of stiffness recovery and oblique cracking can be introduced. The damage model parameters are identified from standard test methods. Comparisons to specific experimental data of UD- and multi directional laminates show good agreement between test data and model predictions.

Table 2: Material data and damage parameters of carbon fiber/epoxy UD-layer, AS4/3501-6 [12].

elastic constants					
E_1	$E_2 = E_3$	$G_{12} = G_{13}$	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	ν_{23}	
[GPa]	[GPa]	[GPa]			
45.6	16.2	5.5	0.278	0.4	
strength data					
	R_{11}	R_{22}	R_{12}	p_{12}	p_{23}
	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]		
tension	1280	40	73	0.3 *	0.22 *
compression	520	145	73	0.25 *	0.22 *
damage evolution		damage effect			
	κ_{12}	κ_{22}^t	e_n	ξ_{sat}	
	0.6	0.1	0.086	0.7	

* following Puck's guidelines for glass fiber materials [18]

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